

Constructs	Code	Items
Task technology fit	TTF1	" The AIGC drawing tools meet my creative design needs " .
	TTF2	" AIGC drawing tools integrate seamlessly with my design process " .
	TTF3	" AIGC drawing tools simplify brainstorming creative ideas for me " .
Self-efficacy	SE1	" I can learn AIGC drawing tools on my own.
	SE2	" AIGC drawing tools enhance my creative thinking efficiency " .
	SE3	" I will seek help from classmates or teachers if needed " .
Subjective norm	SN1	" I accept recommendations to use AIGC drawing tools for creativity " .
	SN2	" Social media success stories encourage me to use AIGC drawing tools " .
	SN3	" Many people in design believe AIGC drawing tools enhance creativity " .
Perceived usefulness	PU1	" AIGC drawing tools inspire my design creativity " .
	PU2	" AIGC drawing tools help me discover new creative possibilities " .
	PU3	" AIGC drawing tools help break creative bottlenecks and provide solutions " .
Expectation confirmation	EC1	" AIGC drawing tools exceeded my expectations in creativity support " .
	EC2	" The user experience with AIGC drawing tools exceeded my expectations " .
	EC3	" Most of my expectations for AIGC drawing tools were met " .
Satisfaction	SAT1	" I ' m satisfied with the creative solutions from AIGC drawing tools " .
	SAT2	" I enjoy using AIGC drawing tools for design " .
	SAT3	" I prefer AIGC drawing tools over traditional design methods " .
Continuance intention	CI1	" I plan to continue using AIGC drawing tools for creative solutions " .
	CI2	" I plan to use AIGC drawing tools more frequently " .
	CI3	" I will recommend AIGC drawing tools for product creative thinking " .